

Supporting Information for Distinguishing Species Boundaries from Geographic Variation

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Supporting Methods

Population Genetic Structure. We first quantified the amount of variant-based missing data using the *missing* command in Plink 1.9 (1). We then constructed a list of positions to be retained in the final matrix using a custom R script that selected a single SNP that minimized missing data; if more than one SNP contained the same proportions of missing data, one SNP was selected at random. Finally, SNPs were pruned out of the vcf file using the *--positions* function in vcfTools v.0.1.13 (2). Plink 1.9 was also used to convert the resulting LD-pruned vcf into a bed file.

We used ADMIXTURE to examine population genetic structure for the four separate assemblies. We ran a range of *K* values which depended on the assembly (3–15 for the *ATL_MXPL* and *CENTAM* assemblies, 1–15 for the *PACMX* assembly, and 1–10 for the *forreri* assembly; *SI Appendix, Fig. S2*) with five replicates per run, and examined cross-validation error to analyze support for individual assignment into each *K*. ADMIXTURE results were visualized using custom scripts that made use of the *tidyverse* packages in R (3; see GitHub repository for all scripts: <https://github.com/eachambers/pantherana>).

Model-Based Species Delimitation. Hierarchical heuristic species delimitation (HHSD; ref. (4) is an extension of the genealogical divergence index (*gdi*; 5). HHSD takes advantage of the MSC-M (migration) model from BPP (6), allowing users to provide information about observed migration between populations. By doing so, this method is particularly useful in cases in which widespread isolation by distance is suspected in the study taxa (4). A guide tree is provided with information about relatedness among populations, along with assignment of individuals into these populations. Two algorithms can then be used: a merge algorithm, which takes the guide tree and hierarchically merges populations that are undergoing gene flow if (and only if) resulting *gdi* values fall below a user-specified threshold. Typical animal thresholds used have been 0.2 or 0.3 (i.e., if *gdi* values are lower than these thresholds, a single species is supported; ref. 5). The split algorithm, by contrast, begins with a tree in which all populations are a single tip and, in the same way as above but reversed, systematically splits populations from this starting single lineage, ending with the relationships of the input guide tree. Once again, a *gdi* threshold value is provided as the upper value above which two populations are considered two species.

We first verified that there was strong support for relationships between putative species in our guide tree. We examined bootstrap support values from our RAxML-ng phylogeny and ensured that all of these groupings were highly supported (bootstrap support $\geq 98\%$). To reduce computational time and ensure no sites were linked, we reduced input datasets by taking the linkage disequilibrium-pruned datasets provided to ADMIXTURE (*SI Appendix, Table S2*) and further removed sites that were missing in more than 40% of individuals which resulted in datasets containing 12,453, 4,684, and 8,226 loci for the *forreri*, *mxpl*, and *foothills* groupings, respectively. We retrieved full loci (i.e., including all sites – invariant and variant – at each locus) and assembled each dataset into a Phylip file using custom scripts (see GitHub repository). Based on results from migration rate prior tests (see details below), HHSD was run using a migration rate prior set to $G(0.1, 20)$ for the 40% missing datasets.

For each of the three datasets, we conducted three separate HHSD runs with different migration rate priors. Due to extreme computational demands of HHSD, we downsampled our datasets for these migration prior tests by removing sites that were missing in more than 25%, 32.5%, or 30% of individuals which retained 848, 1,202, or 1,835 loci in the *forreri*, *mxpl*, and *foothills* groupings, respectively. Specified using a gamma prior $G(\alpha, \beta)$, we set migration rate priors to $G(0.1, 20)$, $G(0.1, 10)$, and $G(2, 20)$ which corresponded to means of 0.005, 0.01, and 0.1 migrants per generation.

Supporting Results

Phylogenetic Tree. A total of 245,016 SNPs were retained after potentially invariant sites were removed for input into RAxML-ng. The mean bootstrap support value across all nodes of the tree was 61.09%; 41.5% of nodes had high support (bootstrap support values $\geq 80\%$). Bootstrap support was high (100%) for *Pantherana*, *Zweifelia*, *Scurrilirana*, and *Lacusirana* nodes, while the *R. pipiens* + *Lacusirana* node had a bootstrap support of 74%.

Contrary to previous phylogenies for the group, we found *R. pustulosa*, not *R. sierramadrensis*, to be most basal to the remaining three outgroup species that were included (*R. sierramadrensis*, *R. psilonota*, and *R. zweifelia*), meaning that the *Torrentirana* group was not supported (Fig. 1 and [SI Appendix, Fig. S4](#)). Further sampling and expanded analyses of this group are required to confirm this finding. Within *Pantherana*, *R. pipiens* was found to be sister to the *Lacusirana* group, a finding consistent with other studies that used mitochondrial and nuclear datasets (7, 8) but contrary to studies using allozyme data that placed this species as sister to *R. blairi* and *R. sphenoccephala* (9).

A single phylogenetic group contained all three species from the Central Mexican Plateau and northern Atlantic coast of Mexico (*R. berlandieri*, *R. neovolcanica*, and *R. tlaloci*) but excluded *R. spectabilis* (Fig. 1 and [SI Appendix, Fig. S4](#)). These relationships were consistent with previous phylogenies (7, 8), although inconsistent with these studies in the distant placement of *R. spectabilis* from this group. Relationships within the group containing species occurring in the foothills of the Sierra Madre Occidental (*R. magnaocularis* and *R. yavapaiensis*) were consistent with previous findings except that our phylogenetic tree included *R. omiltemana* within this group.

Model-Based Species Delimitation. HHSD was robust to migration rate priors in that *gdi* estimates for pairs of comparisons did not differ substantially ([SI Appendix, Fig. S6](#)); the reduced dataset sizes that we used for testing these parameters also did not impact *gdi* estimation (compare *gdi* values in [SI Appendix, Fig. S6](#) with those in [SI Appendix, Table S3](#)). There were two exceptions to this. The first was for the *foothills* group, in which split algorithms supported either 1 or 6 species as the final delimitation. To remain as consistent as possible across algorithms while taking into consideration the ranges of *gdi* estimates for population pairs, we supported six species in our final delimitation for this group. The second exception was varying support for *chichicuahutla* as a distinct lineage within the *mxpl* group. However, in the HHSD run that supported *chichicuahutla* as being distinct (which used the split algorithm), we observed borderline *gdi* estimates for both *chichicuahutla* (0.63) and *spectabilis* (0.73).

Landscape Genomics in the *R. forreri* Complex. We performed all landscape genomic analyses at the site level; our analysis included 1–14 individuals collected at 38 separate localities. Conversion of our vcf to a genotype dosage matrix resulted in the removal of 951 non-biallelic sites, leaving 64,049 remaining upon which all subsequent landscape genomics analyses were performed.

Taxonomic History of the Leopard Frog Species Complex

Hillis et al. (9) conducted the first large-scale genetic work on the leopard frog species complex (*R. pipiens* complex), using allozyme data to designate three species groups (*montezumae*, *areolata*, and *berlandieri*) as well as to identify a basal split corresponding with a Northern–Southern vicariance (which they designated the alpha and beta divisions). They also provided support for nine undescribed species which they found belonged to three broad geographic regions of Mexico: the coastal regions, the foothills of the Sierra Madre Occidental, and the Central Mexican Plateau. Four of these species (*R. tlaloci*, *R. neovolcanica*, *R. spectabilis*, and *R. yavapaiensis*) were subsequently formally recognized.

In 2005, Zaldívar-Riverón et al. (10) used mitochondrial DNA to confirm the validity of *R. brownorum* as a species as it had been split from *R. berlandieri* (11), and clarified the phylogenetic relationships of the Pacific coastal group (i.e., *R. forreri*), including three undescribed species proposed by Hillis et al. (9): the Papagayo, Arcelia, and Colima forms. Zaldívar-Riverón et al. (10) found that although the Arcelia and Colima forms were nested within the *R. forreri* clade, the Papagayo form was most closely related to individuals from the Pacific foothills (e.g., *R. magnaocularis*), rather than to the coastal *R. forreri* individuals.

In 2005, Hillis and Wilcox (7) re-evaluated the *Pantherana* subgenus using mitochondrial DNA and found relationships which largely supported those of Hillis et al. (9), with the exception of the placement of *R. pipiens* on their phylogeny which altered the compositions of the alpha and beta divisions (*R. pipiens* moved from the beta to the alpha division). They also sequenced two of the still undescribed species from Hillis et al. (9), the Atenquique short- and long-forms (which they named sp. 7 and 8, respectively), along with three other putative undescribed species within *Pantherana* from Panamá and Costa Rica (named sp. 4, 5, and 6).

Hillis and Wilcox (7) modified the earlier species groups of (9) by describing four divisions within the subgenus based on phylogenetic relationships and call descriptions, which they named *Stertirana* (the *R. montezumae* species group from ref. 9, plus *R. pipiens*), *Lacusirana* (the *R. montezumae* species group from ref. 9), *Nenirana* (the *R. areolata* species group from ref. 9), and *Scurrilirana* (the *R. berlandieri* species group from ref. 9). The latter group, *Scurrilirana*, included most of the diversity in southern and tropical leopard frogs and was thus the focus of this manuscript. The most recent phylogenetic work on the complex in 2016 conducted a Holarctic analysis of the genus *Rana* (8), and provided updated phylogenetic relationships in some members of *Pantherana* based on nuclear and mitochondrial gene regions. This work found relationships that were largely consistent with those from (7).

In the years since, several more leopard frog species have been formally described in Mexico and Central America. A species reported to be endemic to a crater lake in Puebla, *R. chichicuahutla*, was described based on color pattern characters (12). An integrative taxonomic approach using a combination of morphological characters, call data, and genetic sequencing, resulted in the description of a new species from the complex in the highlands of central Honduras, *R. lenca* (13). Most recently, *R. forreri* was split into five species (four new) based solely on color pattern differences: from north to south, *R. adleri*, *R. forreri*, *R. cora*, *R. floresi*, and *R. hillisi* (14, 15). Many of these samples were collected at the same localities as samples from Zaldívar-Riverón et al. (10); in fact, both *R. adleri* and *R. cora* share the same mitochondrial haplotype with an individual from the type locality of *R. forreri* (Villa Unión, Sinaloa; see [SI Appendix, Note on the type localities of *R. forreri*, *R. macroglossa*, and *R. omiltemana*](#)). Both *R. hillisi* and *R. floresi* share the same mitochondrial haplotype with two Colima form individuals referred to in Zaldívar-Riverón et al. (10) along the coastal regions of the Sierra Madre del Sur ([SI Appendix, Fig. S3](#)).

Taxonomic Recommendations

Pacific Coastal Lowlands. We recognize a single, widespread, geographically variable species along the Pacific coast from Sonora, Mexico, south to Guanacaste Province, Costa Rica, as *R. forreri*. This species exhibits geographic variation in color pattern and genetic population structure that is expected across a species with such an extensive range. However, our analyses do not support any consistent reproductive breaks among the variable populations; rather, the observed geographic variation is consistent with isolation by distance and isolation by environment. Our analysis included five named taxa that we consider conspecific with *R. forreri*: *R. miadis*, described in ref. (16); and *R. adleri*, *R. cora*, *R. floresi*, and *R. hillisi*, described in refs. (14, 15). These taxa also included samples that were informally called the Arcelia and Colima forms (9) and (10). We did find geographic and genetic structure consistent with recognizing four subspecies of *R. forreri* (Fig. 2C, 3B, and SI Appendix, Fig. S5C and D): *R. f. forreri* (from Sonora south to Nayarit), *R. f. floresi* (from Jalisco south to Colima and Michoacán), *R. f. hillisi* (south and east of the Río Balsas, in Guerrero and Oaxaca, south and east to the Isthmus of Tehuantepec), and *R. f. miadis* (from the Isthmus of Tehuantepec south and east to Guanacaste, Costa Rica). Based on our species delimitation analysis, we found that the Arcelia form (in the interior Balsas Basin) was also distinct from a population genetic structure perspective (Fig. 2C), although paraphyletic with respect to the members within the *R. forreri* complex on our reconstructed phylogeny (Fig. 1 and SI Appendix, Fig. S4).

The application of the name *R. f. miadis* to the southernmost geographic race of *R. forreri* requires some explanation. *Rana miadis* was described from Little Corn Island, Nicaragua (16), a small island approximately 70 kilometers east of the mainland of Nicaragua (on the Atlantic side of Central America). Little Corn Island only reaches a maximum elevation of 38 meters, and it has a flora and fauna generally similar to that of the Caribbean coast of Nicaragua, with a few notable exceptions. Our data indicate that populations of leopard frogs on Little Corn Island are genetically indistinguishable from populations of *Rana forreri* on the Pacific coast of Nicaragua from a phylogenetic (Fig. 1A and B, and SI Appendix, Fig. S4), population genetic structure (Fig. 3B, and SI Appendix, Fig. S5D), and landscape genomic (Fig. 5) standpoint. While unexpected, this pattern is consistent with that seen in at least two species of snakes, *Coniophanes piceivittis* and *Pseudelaphe flavirufa*, the iguana *Ctenosaura similis*, and the mangrove cuckoo *Coccyzus minor*, each of which have been recorded in the Corn Islands and yet are absent from adjacent Caribbean coastal areas of Nicaragua but otherwise widely distributed along the Pacific slope (17–19). Although the geological origin of the Corn Islands is not well-understood, Alvarado et al. (20) suggested a volcanic origin during the Pleistocene, with the contemporary depth of the sea between the mainland and islands not exceeding a maximum of 25 meters (with depths <2m across the majority of the area). We infer that the Little Corn Island leopard frogs were either introduced to the island from the Pacific coast of Central America (likely western Nicaragua), or found their way via recent dispersal, potentially aided by one or more of three major rivers flowing from the Pacific side of Nicaragua to the Caribbean. Nonetheless, this is the oldest name available for the southernmost geographical race of *R. forreri*.

The remaining two named taxa, *R. adleri* and *R. cora*, are junior synonyms of *R. f. forreri*. Our phylogenetic and population structure results (Fig. 1A and B, and 3B) were largely congruent with those from the mitochondrial data by Zaldívar-Riverón et al. (10), which show samples referable to “*R. cora*” and “*R. adleri*” as virtually identical to typotypic *R. forreri* (from Sinaloa). Among the subspecies we recognize, the only taxon that does not show extensive gene flow (Fig. 3B and SI Appendix, Fig. S5D) to the other subspecies in our analyses is *R. f. hillisi*. However, this is likely related to sampling gaps between our samples of *R. f. hillisi* and *R. forreri floresi* on one end of the range of *R. f. hillisi*, and between *R. f. hillisi* and *R. f. miadis* on other. Nonetheless, the phylogenetic structure of these populations (SI Appendix, Fig.

S5D) is consistent with *R. f. hillisi* as one of several north–south geographic groupings of *R. forreri* along the Pacific coast of Mexico and Central America.

Atlantic Coast. Despite limited geographic coverage in our study, it appears that *R. macroglossa* is far more wide-ranging than was previously thought. The holotype of the species was described from the “plateau of Guatemala” (21), although the original type series included both a leopard frog and a member of the *R. maculata* species group (22). To clarify application of the name, Smith and coworkers (22) designated MNHNP 6321, a leopard frog, as the lectotype for *R. macroglossa* (at the time, it was considered a junior synonym of *R. pipiens*). D.M.H. examined MNHNP 6321 in the early 1980s and confirmed its identity as a leopard frog. Although this species is indeed found in the central highlands of Guatemala, our analyses indicate that the species is widely distributed northward into the Atlantic coastal lowlands and Pacific foothills of southern Mexico, and southward along the Atlantic versant through Honduras and Nicaragua into Costa Rica. The contact zone between *R. macroglossa* and *R. berlandieri* appears to occur at or near the approach of the Transvolcanic Belt to the Gulf of Mexico (Fig. 2B and SI Appendix, Fig. S3), although additional sampling is required to confirm the details of this contact zone. Nonetheless, we recognize the two species as distinct, as they do not appear to be one another’s closest relatives (SI Appendix, Fig. S4) or show any signs of hybridization. *Rana taylori* (20) was described to accommodate a series of spotted frogs from “Peralta, Costa Rica”, first reported by Taylor (23) as *R. maculata*. Savage (24) clarified the type locality to be “Peralta, Cantón de Turrialba, Provincia de Cartago, 368 m”, a lowland locality on the Atlantic slope, and later Savage (25) applied the name *R. taylori* to all leopard frog populations from the Atlantic coast and central highlands of Costa Rica, noting that the highland populations likely represented an undescribed and relatively small species distinct from other Costa Rican forms. Based on the restricted type locality, we infer that the name *R. taylori* refers to a population representing the southern terminus of Atlantic Coast leopard frog distributions. These results indicate that *R. berlandieri brownorum* (11, 26) and *R. taylori* (27) are junior synonyms of *R. macroglossa* (Fig. 2A).

Pacific Foothills. Our results strongly support a group of related species in the Pacific foothills, from Arizona and Utah in the United States, south through the Sierra Madre del Sur of southern Mexico (SI Appendix, Fig. S3). Several species in this group are sympatric with *R. forreri* along the Pacific coast (28). *Rana magnaocularis* occurs at lower elevation localities in southern Sonora, Sinaloa, and Nayarit, and Jalisco and is a member of a Pacific foothills group, which also includes the closely related species *R. yavapaiensis* and *R. onca* of the United States (SI Appendix, Fig. S4; 29–31). The oldest name available among these three species is *R. onca* (32). Until more sampling and study of these taxa is conducted, we recommend them to be referable together as the *R. onca* complex, based on the oldest available name for the group.

Two successively more distantly related lineages of the Pacific foothills group occur to the south, in the Mexican states of Jalisco, Colima, and Puebla (north and west of the Balsas Basin formed by the Balsas River; SI Appendix, Fig. S3). These two taxa have been called the Atenquique short- and Atenquique long-forms, as they have been collected sympatrically near Atenquique, Jalisco (9). The Atenquique short-form appears to be most closely related to the *R. onca* complex, whereas the Atenquique long-form is the most divergent species in this clade (SI Appendix, Fig. S4). However, better sampling and analysis is needed to fully understand the species boundaries in the *R. onca* complex and the related Atenquique short- and long-forms.

In the foothills and highlands of the Sierra Madre del Sur, farther south along the Pacific coast (in Guerrero and Oaxaca, south of the Balsas Basin), an additional species forms the sister-group of the *R. onca* complex plus the Atenquique short- and long-forms. *Rana omiltemana* was described from

Omiteme (=Omitemi), Guerrero (33), and is the oldest name available for this species; therefore, this name has been applied to leopard frog populations in the Sierra Madre del Sur of Guerrero (e.g., ref. 8). Our analyses suggest that this species extends south into the Sierra Madre del Sur of Oaxaca as well (Fig. 1C). Some populations of this species were called the Papagayo form by Hillis et al. (9). Consistent with mitochondrial data (10), the Papagayo form is not a member of the coastal complex as proposed by Hillis et al. (9), but rather is a member of the Pacific foothills group. Given phylogenetic relationships and our population structure analyses (Fig. 2C), the Oaxaca populations in the Sierra Madre del Sur represent southern populations of *R. omitemana*. Our data also show differentiation between populations of *R. omitemana* in the Sierra Madre del Sur of Guerrero from related populations in the Sierra Madre del Sur of Oaxaca, but our sampling was not sufficient to designate any subspecies, and no names are currently available for the Oaxaca populations.

Central Mexican Plateau and Transvolcanic Belt. *Rana spectabilis* occurs at higher elevations of the Transvolcanic Belt, especially in pine and fir forests from Michoacán to Hidalgo and Puebla (Fig. 1, 2, and *SI Appendix, Fig. S3*; 34), and these populations exhibit the brilliant metallic green coloration that gives the species its name (which means “showy”). Although Hillis and Frost (34) included lower-elevation populations to the south, in Puebla and Oaxaca, in this species, these southern populations tend to exhibit less of the bright green coloration. One population of *R. spectabilis* in Puebla was described as a new species, *R. chichicuahutla* (12). Our analyses support these two taxa being conspecific north-south geographic variation within *R. spectabilis*, with considerable gene flow and intermediates between the northern brightly colored populations, and southern less brightly colored populations. Given differences in population genetics and coloration between the two groups of populations, we suggest the recognition of two subspecies within *R. spectabilis*, namely *R. s. spectabilis* in the north, and *R. s. chichicuahutla* in the south, with the following caveats. First, the holotype and paratype specimens of *R. chichicuahutla* were said to be deposited in the Museo de Zoología “Alfonso L. Herrera” at the Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, but the collection numbers were never identified and specimens that fit the type descriptions are not currently present in the collection (O.F.V. and G.C.G., personal observations). It appears that the type specimens were never deposited or have been lost, so we could not examine type specimens to verify our assignment of this taxon. Nonetheless, a color photograph of the holotype in the original description of *R. chichicuahutla* is typical of specimens from the southern range of *R. spectabilis*. Second, A.Y.C.B. attempted to find leopard frogs at the type locality of *R. chichicuahutla* several times, but it appears that leopard frogs are now extinct at this locality. We instead sampled individuals from localities as close as possible to the type locality and with similar environmental conditions; these individuals were phenotypically similar to southern *R. spectabilis* and to photographs of the type specimen of *R. chichicuahutla* from the species description (12). Therefore, all information appears to be consistent in treating *R. chichicuahutla* as a southern subspecies of *R. spectabilis*.

One of us (G.C.G.) identified a population of leopard frogs from the Chilpancingo region in Guerrero that appears to represent an isolated population of *R. spectabilis* based on morphology and mitochondrial sequencing (genomic data for these individuals was not included in the present study). Unless new populations of *R. spectabilis* are discovered in the mountains of eastern Guerrero, where suitable habitat exists for this widespread species, we assume that it has been introduced into the Chilpancingo region, as all other leopard frogs we have sequenced from the Sierra Madre del Sur of Guerrero represent the distantly related *R. omitemana* (Fig. 2C).

The populations of leopard frogs that occur across lower (more northerly) elevations of the Neovolcanic Plateau of central Mexico were described as *R. neovolcanica* and *R. tlaloci* by Hillis and Frost (34). These species differ from *R. berlandieri* in the Atlantic lowlands mostly in size (adults are smaller) and in lacking vestigial oviducts in males. Our analyses show no clear reproductive break between *R. berlandieri*, *R.*

neovolcanica, and *R. tlaloci*, and a number of genetic intermediates among these taxa. Given the nested placement of *R. tlaloci* on our phylogenetic tree within samples of *R. neovolcanica*, and the close relationship (with no distinct genetic break, and genetic intermediates) between *R. berlandieri* and *R. neovolcanica* (*SI Appendix*, Fig. S5A), we consider these three putative taxa to represent geographically variable populations of *R. berlandieri*. Given described genetic and morphological differences between highland and lowland populations (34), we recognize *R. b. neovolcanica* as a subspecies of *R. berlandieri*, and treat *R. tlaloci* as a subjective junior synonym of *R. b. neovolcanica*. *Rana neovolcanica* and *R. tlaloci* were described in the same paper (34); as first revisors, we here select the more widely distributed *R. b. neovolcanica* as the name of these two taxa.

Lower Central America. Based on phylogenetic relationships and population structure (Fig. 3C and *SI Appendix*, Fig. S4), we found distinct diversity occurring across high elevation mountains of Costa Rica and extending into Panamá, consistent with descriptions by Hillis and Wilcox (7) and later Luque-Montes and coworkers (13) in their description of *R. lenca*. We recommend further sampling to validate the species status of these populations. Our results suggest that Hillis and Wilcox's (7) sp. 4 and 5 belong to this group, whereas the lowland sp. 6 (from Puntarenas) appears to belong to *R. f. miadis* (*SI Appendix*, Fig. S4), the species that occurs in the Pacific coastal lowlands of Guanacaste Province.

Note on the type localities of *R. forreri* and *R. macroglossa*, and *R. omiltemana*

***Rana forreri*.** In the late 19th century, Alphonso Forrer collected a number of specimens from a locality he described as "Presidio, Sinaloa" which were deposited at the British Museum of Natural History in London. These samples became the type specimens for several species, including *R. forreri* (BMNH 1882.12.5.7; 35). Presidio, Sinaloa is not a currently used name for any site, city, or town in the Mexican state of Sinaloa. As the word "presidio" is translated to "fort" from Spanish, it is possible that this locality is not a proper noun but rather simply describing a fort present in the state of Sinaloa. However, a number of authors later providing commentary or taxonomic revisions to several species described at this locality state the locality as "Presidio de Mazatlan" by Kellogg in 1932 (36: page 212), or "Presidio, near Mazatlan, Sinaloa, Mexico" by Oliver in 1943 (37: page 97).

The town of Presidio de Mazatlán had its name changed in 1828 to Villa Unión (<https://centrohistoricomazatlan.mx/historia-del-puerto-comerciante/>) and is a city located approximately 20 kilometers south of Mazatlán and on the southern banks of the Presidio River. Thus, the type locality for *R. forreri* is at Villa Unión, Sinaloa, Mexico. This is confirmed through an account by Löwenstern (38) who traveled from Mexico City to Mazatlán in 1841. Löwenstern describes the following:

El Rosario [Sinaloa] appears to be the centre of the trade between the port of Mazatlan and the interior. Its population exceeds 5000. To the Rancho of Potrerrillo 4 leagues; to Casa de Teja 4 to 6 leagues; to El Rincon 2 leagues; to La Canita ½ a league; to the Presidio de Mazatlan, with broad streets and large buildings, and more than 1500 inhabitants, 4 leagues. The wide and rapid Rio de Mazatlan [the Presidio River] is forded ½ a league further on: then the road continues, 5 leagues through a mountainous and sterile country, without water: then over downs, and by lagoons fordable at high water, after 5 leagues more, bring the traveller to the Puerto de Mazatlan, now the most frequented port on this coast...

It is also worth noting that the nomenclature for this locality has been propagated through the literature, and is the type locality for at least eight other species or subspecies of reptiles or amphibians: *Trachycephalus "vermiculatus"* (39), *Smilisca fodiens* (40), *Triprrion spatulatus* (41), *Hypopachus*

variolosus (35, 36, 42), *Gyalopion quadrangulare* (33), *Masticophis lineatus* (43), *Sceloporus clarkii boulengeri* (44), and *Urosaurus ornatus lateralis* (35, 37).

***Rana macroglossa*.** A specific type locality for *R. macroglossa* was not provided when the species was described (17), but rather stated as the “plateau of Guatemala”. Within Guatemala, two possibilities exist for the placement of the type locality given the terminology of a “plateau”: either the Petén department, which encompasses a low elevation limestone plateau in the northern parts of the country, or the highlands of the country that span south-central Guatemala. We believe the type locality is in the central highlands for two reasons. First, the manuscript describing the species was written in French, and “plateau” is directly translated to “highlands”. Secondly, the type specimen of *R. macroglossa* was collected by Bocourt and was documented in 1870 (45). Based on a map of Bocourt’s travel throughout Guatemala during this trip (left-hand panel below), he did not travel to the Petén department at all, rather traveling through south-central parts of the country which coincide with regions of high elevation. Thus, we place the type locality of *R. macroglossa* within the high elevation regions in which Bocourt traveled (orange polygon in right-hand panel below).

***Rana omiltemana*.** The type locality of *R. omiltemana* is “Omilteme in Guerrero 8000 feet” (33); this locality may represent an upper elevational limit for this species, as *R. omiltemana* typically inhabits lower elevation foothills of the Sierra Madre del Sur. Interestingly, *R. spectabilis* has also been recorded near Omiltemi (by G.C.G.), where we suspect it has been recently introduced. Examination of photographs confirmed that the syntypes of *R. omiltemana* (BMNH 1947.2.2.52–56) are well-preserved and their dorsal pattern is still visible. From this examination, we concluded that the illustration accompanying the original description of *R. omiltemana* is based on different specimens from the syntypes, due to the differences displayed in the dorsal pattern and the rounded, rather than pointed, snout shape of specimens. Unfortunately, *R. omiltemana* appears to be extinct in Omiltemi, likely because of channeling of water towards the city of Chilpancingo (46).

Supporting Figures

1. Hypothesis formation about putative taxa

2. Testing if initial groups represent intra- or interspecific variation

Sympatric taxa

Test for presence of significant reproductive isolation in cases of geographic overlap

Allopatric taxa

Algorithms to test for gene flow across geographic space

Present

Absent

Distinct species

Intraspecific polymorphism

Congruent results

Combine or accept taxa based on results

Conflicting results

Not feasible; data unavailable

Match taxa to divergence of existing related taxa until explicit tests can be conducted

3. Additional tests for intraspecific variation or presence of gene flow

Fig. S1. Species delimitation workflow used in the present study.

Fig. S2. Historical examination of the taxonomy within the *Rana pipiens* complex (modified from ref. 47) demonstrating the number of species recognized at the time (red line) and cumulative number of currently accepted species (black line). Major paradigm shifts related to accepted species concepts are indicated in colored boxes, with relevant time points indicated with labeled dashed lines. Details on taxonomic revisions are provided in *SI Appendix*, Taxonomic History of the Leopard Frog Species Complex, Taxonomic Recommendations, and Table S1. Details on species descriptions can be found in *SI Appendix*, Table S4.

Fig. S3. Elevational profile and regions in Mexico referred to in text. Indicated regions combine the following Mexican biogeographic provinces: Central Mexican Plateau (includes high plains north and south provinces); Atlantic Coastal Lowlands (includes Tamaulipas, Gulf of Mexico, Yucatán, and Petén provinces); Pacific Coastal Lowlands (includes Sonoran and Pacific coast provinces); Sierra Madre de Chiapas (includes Soconusco and Chiapas highlands provinces); Sierra Madre de Oaxaca (includes the Oaxaca province). The remaining five indicated regions (Sierra Madre Occidental, Sierra Madre Oriental, Sierra Madre del Sur, Transvolcanic Belt, and Balsas Basin) are equivalent to biogeographic provinces. For simplicity, we have omitted the three Mexican biogeographic provinces that are within the states of Baja California del Norte and del Sur (California, Baja California, and del Cabo) as they fall outside the current study's region of interest. Dashed lines indicate Mexican state boundaries. Biogeographic provinces modified based on map provided in (48).

Scurrilirana

Hidalgo
Michoacán
Morelos
Oaxaca
Papagayo form
Guerrero
Papagayo form
Arizona
Nayarit
Sonora
Jalisco
Puebla
Jalisco
Sinaloa
Nayarit
Jalisco
Colima
Jalisco
Colima form
Guerrero
Nicaragua
Guatemala
Chiapas
Oaxaca
Chiapas
Oaxaca
Chiapas
Oaxaca
Nicaragua

R. spectabilis
R. omiltemana
R. yavapaiensis
R. magnaocularis
Atenquique short
Atenquique long
R. forneri
R. floresii
R. hillisi
R. forneri
R. f. miadis

type locality "miadis"

Fig. S4. Phylogeny for pooled assembly ($n = 479$) reconstructed using maximum likelihood in RAxML-ng (49, 50). Tip labels are consistent with sample identifiers from bioinformatics analysis; tip circles are colorized according to the best K value obtained from ADMIXTURE results (see *SI Appendix*, Fig. S5). Collection localities at the state level (for Mexico and the United States; remaining countries labeled at the country level) are indicated in gray. If applicable, relevant information (e.g., paratypes, holotypes, specimens collected at type localities, specimens collected at sympatric localities, or undescribed species numbers from (7)) are provided in bolded gray text. Bootstrap support values indicated as colored node circles. Four separate assemblies used for analyses are indicated on the right-hand side of the figure; darker gray bars indicate individuals that were included. Abbreviations: *ATL_MXPL*: individuals from the Central Mexican Plateau, Transvolcanic Belt, Sierra Madre Oriental and northern Atlantic Coastal Lowlands; *PACMX*: individuals from the Pacific Coastal Lowlands and Balsas Basin; *CENTAM*: individuals from Central America; *forreri*: individuals belonging to the *R. forreri* complex.

A

Figure S6. Heuristic hierarchical species delimitation (4) results for (A) the Pacific Coastal Lowlands and Balsas Basin (*forreri* grouping); (B) the foothills of the Sierra Madre Occidental and the Sierra Madre del Sur, and the western Transvolcanic Belt (*foothills* grouping); and (C) the Central Mexican Plateau and Atlantic Coastal Lowlands (*mxpl* grouping) for both HHS merge (left) and split (right) algorithms. Bars above guide trees indicate which populations were considered in HHS analysis and are colorized according to estimated *gdi* value. Bars are ordered bottom to top based on iterative merges or splits made by HHS. Dotted lines connecting bars indicate which populations were compared.

Fig. S7. Mantel test results for the *R. forreri* complex (*forreri* assembly; $n = 103$). The Mantel r statistic was 0.77 (p -value = 0.001).

Fig. S8. (A) Environmental values for the third highest principal component from a raster PCA for the *R. forreri* complex study area with sampling localities used in landscape genomic analyses indicated as black circles; white lines denote country borders and Mexican states. (B) Bioclimatic variables that were included in our landscape genomic analyses loaded onto the first and third highest principal components from a raster PCA. Bioclimatic variables 13 and 14 (BIO 13 and BIO 14) loaded highly onto raster PC3 and correspond to precipitation of the wettest and driest months, respectively.

Fig. S9. Results from cross-validation analysis from Fast Estimation of Effective Migration Surfaces (52, 53). Red dashed line indicates selected lambda value (20) which minimized cross-validation error.

Supporting Tables

Table S1. Currently recognized species within the *Scurrilirana* subgroup within the *R. pipiens* complex (*Pantherana*), indicating numbers of individuals that were included and taxonomic recommendations of the current study. Also included are undescribed species from (9) and (7) for which representatives were included in this study.

Species (year described)	Representatives included in current study post/prior to removal ¹	Country-level degree of endemism	IUCN Red List of Threatened Species Status / SEMARNAT NOM-059 Status	Taxonomic recommendations of current study
<i>R. adleri</i> (2023)	Presumed by locality ²	ME	– / –	Synonymized with <i>R. forreri</i>
<i>R. berlandieri</i> (1859)	35 (37)	ME, US	LC / Pr	Recognized
<i>R. blairi</i> (1973)	2 (2)	US	LC / –	Recognized
<i>R. brownorum</i> (1973)	26 (33)	BE, GU, HO, ME, NI	LC / Pr	Synonymized with <i>R. macroglossa</i>
<i>R. chichicuahutla</i> (1996)	Presumed by locality	ME	CR / –	Synonymized with <i>R. spectabilis</i> ; recognized as subspecies
<i>R. cora</i> (2022)	Presumed by locality ²	ME	– / –	Synonymized with <i>R. forreri</i>
<i>R. floresi</i> (2022)	Presumed by locality ²	ME	– / –	Synonymized with <i>R. forreri</i> ; recognized as subspecies
<i>R. forreri</i> (1883)	95 (102) (includes <i>R. adleri</i> , <i>R. cora</i> , <i>R. floresi</i> , and <i>R. hillisi</i> , which were presumed by locality ²)	CR, ES, GU, HO, ME, NI	LC / Pr	Recognized
<i>R. hillisi</i> (2023)	Presumed by locality ²	ME	– / –	Synonymized with <i>R. forreri</i> ; recognized as subspecies
<i>R. lenca</i> (2018)	31 (33)	HO	EN / –	Recognized
<i>R. macroglossa</i> (1877)	52 (57)	BE, CR, ES, GU, HO, ME, NI	VU / –	Recognized

<i>R. magnaocularis</i> (1974)	13 (14)	ME	LC / –	Recognized (as part of <i>R. onca</i> complex, which requires additional study)
<i>R. miadis</i> (1929)	3 (4)	ME	CR / –	Synonymized with <i>R. forreri</i> ; recognized as subspecies
<i>R. neovolcanica</i> (1985)	11 (11)	ME	LC / A	Synonymized with <i>R. berlandieri</i> ; recognized as subspecies
<i>R. omiltemana</i> (1900)	4 (4)	ME	EN / P	Recognized
<i>R. onca</i> (1875)	None	US	EN / –	Not examined (oldest available name for the <i>R. onca</i> complex, which includes <i>R. magnaocularis</i> and <i>R. yavapaiensis</i>).
<i>R. spectabilis</i> (1985)	70 (74) (includes <i>R. chichicuahutla</i> , which was presumed by locality and population structure results)	ME	LC / –	Recognized
<i>R. sphenoccephala</i> (1826)	2 (2)	US	LC / –	Recognized
<i>R. taylori</i> (1959)	4 (7)	CR, NI	LC / –	Synonymized with <i>R. macroglossa</i>
<i>R. tlaloci</i> (1985)	1 (2)	ME	CR / P	Synonymized with <i>R. berlandieri</i>
<i>R. yavapaiensis</i> (1984)	4 (4)	ME, US	LC / Pr	Recognized (as part of <i>R. onca</i> complex, which requires additional study)
Sp. 4 (7); PM: Chiriquí)	3 (4)	PM	N/A	New species (together with sp. 5); additional diagnosis required to formally describe
Sp. 5 (7); CR: Heredia)	4 (5)	CR	N/A	New species (together with sp. 4); additional diagnosis required to formally describe
Sp. 6 (7); CR:	10 (11)	CR	N/A	Synonymized with <i>R. forreri</i>

Puntareñas)				
Atenquique short-form (9) or sp. 7 (7)	4 (5)	ME	N/A	New species; additional diagnosis required to formally describe
Atenquique long-form (9) or sp. 8 (7)	3 (3)	ME	N/A	New species; additional diagnosis required to formally describe
Papagayo form (9)	50 (52)	ME	N/A	Part of <i>R. omiltemana</i>
Arcelia form (9)	2 (3)	ME	N/A	Unnamed geographic variation within <i>R. forreri</i>
Colima form (9)	3 (3)	ME	N/A	Part of <i>R. f. floresii</i>

¹Numbers in parentheses indicate the number of individuals within each species prior to the removal of individuals with fewer than 10,000 SNPs; numbers not in parentheses are the number of individuals included in analyses because they had more than 10,000 SNPs.

²Presumed by locality based on information and range maps provided by (14, 15).

Abbreviations: BE: Belize; CA: Canada; CR: Costa Rica; ES: El Salvador; GU: Guatemala; HO: Honduras; ME: Mexico; NI: Nicaragua; PM: Panama; US: United States of America; ND: no data, IUCN; LC: least concern status, IUCN; NT: near threatened status, IUCN; EN: endangered status, IUCN; CR: critically endangered status, IUCN; Pr: special protection status, NOM-059; P: endangered status, NOM-059; A: threatened status, NOM-059.

Table S2. Basic statistics for assemblies generated using iPyrad v.0.9.85 (54).

Assembly	Number of individuals (prior/post removal ¹)	Read depth ²	No. sites	No. SNPs	Parsimony informative sites ³	No. loci	Average missing data ⁴ (prior/post removal ¹)	No. SNPs after LD pruning ⁵	No. loci for HHSD ⁶
Pooled	527 / 479	17.56	2,262,042	350,292	177,160	15,857	65.30% / 62.80%	N/A	N/A
<i>ATL_MXPL</i>	202 / 189	13.90	7,118,981	718,861	459,423	50,287	59.58% / 56.81%	50,228	4,684 (<i>mxpl</i> individuals only) ⁷
<i>PACMX</i>	274 / 245	21.27	6,403,819	775,665	538,336	45,134	58.16% / 53.23%	45,130	8,226 (<i>foothills</i> individuals only) ⁸
<i>CENTAM</i>	158 / 140	14.12	5,120,329	441,907	286,456	36,186	63.50% / 58.86%	36,126	N/A
<i>forreri</i>	104 / 104	13.00	9,376,150	564,916	375,802	66,511	54.31% / 54.31%	65,000 ⁹	12,453 ¹⁰

¹“Prior/post” refers to assembly numbers prior and post-removal of individuals with fewer than 10,000 SNPs.

²Average statistical read depth, calculated during step 3 of iPyrad.

³As calculated by iPyrad.

⁴Mean individual-based missing data proportions, calculated using Plink v.1.9 (1).

⁵After removal of samples with fewer than 10,000 SNPs, pruning sites in linkage disequilibrium involved first removing any sites with $\geq 75\%$ per-variant missing data proportions, followed by selecting a single SNP per RAD tag (locus) that minimizes per-variant missing data. See Supplementary Materials for further details.

⁶Number of loci (full tags) used for heuristic hierarchical species delimitation (4) analysis; datasets were pruned further from previous analyses based on missing data.

⁷Parameter testing of migration rate priors for HHSD used a downsampled dataset with 1,202 loci.

⁸Parameter testing of migration rate priors for HHSD used a downsampled dataset with 1,835 loci.

⁹This assembly originally had 65,907 SNPs but computational limitations of Plink 1.9 required removal of 907 SNPs resulting in 65,000 SNPs.

¹⁰Parameter testing of migration rate priors for HHSD used a downsampled dataset with 848 loci.

Abbreviations: SNP: Single nucleotide polymorphism; LD: linkage disequilibrium; HHSD: hierarchical heuristic species delimitation.

Table S3. Heuristic hierarchical species delimitation (4) results for three data groupings, three migration rate priors, and for both HHSD merge and split algorithms. See Fig. 4 for a visualization of population assignment groupings used as input populations in HHSD guide tree. The threshold for the genealogical divergence index (*gdi*; ref. 5) was the same for all runs: for merge algorithm, it was set to ≤ 0.3 and for the split algorithm, it was set to ≥ 0.7 . We ran each parameter set for 200,000 generations with 10% of samples discarded as burnin. Results shown for migration priors of (0.1, 10) and (2, 20) are for downsampled datasets while those for priors of (0.1, 20) are for full datasets. See *SI Appendix, Supporting Methods* for details and *SI Appendix, Figure S6* for HHSD results for visualization of results.

Input dataset	Populations in guide tree	Algorithm	Migration prior	Resulting delimitation (no. pops)	Comparison (pop 1 + pop 2) ^{1,2}	Estimated <i>gdi</i> (pop 1 + pop 2) [2.5%–97.5% HPD] ²		
forreri	5	Merge	(0.1, 10)	5	<i>flor + hilli</i>	0.80 [0.77–0.83] + 0.81 [0.78–0.85]		
			(0.1, 20) ³	5	<i>flor + hilli</i>	0.79 + 0.82		
			(2, 20)	5	<i>flor + hilli</i>	0.81 [0.77–0.84] + 0.82 [0.78–0.85]		
		Split	(0.1, 10)	1	<i>flor/hilli/arce/forr + miad</i>	0.56 [0.53–0.59] + 0.61 [0.59–0.64]		
			(0.1, 20) ³	1	<i>flor/hilli/arce/forr + miad</i>	0.57 + 0.61		
			(2, 20)	1	<i>flor/hilli/arce/forr + miad</i>	0.57 [0.54–0.59] + 0.62 [0.59–0.65]		
foothills	6	Merge	(0.1, 10)	6	<i>omio + omig</i> <i>yava + magn</i>	0.93 [0.91–0.94] + 0.93 [0.91–0.94] 0.96 [0.95–0.98] + 0.67 [0.62–0.71]		
			(0.1, 20) ³	6	<i>omio + omig</i> <i>yava + magn</i>	0.94 + 0.93 0.97 + 0.68		
			(2, 20)	6	<i>omio + omig</i> <i>yava + magn</i>	0.95 [0.94–0.96] + 0.95 [0.94–0.96] 0.97 [0.95–0.98] + 0.68 [0.64–0.71]		
			(0.1, 10)	1	<i>yava/magn/ates/atel + omio/omig</i>	0.53 [0.51–0.55] + 0.91 [0.90–0.92]		
		Split	(0.1, 20) ³	6	<i>yava/magn/ates/atel + omio/omig</i>	0.53 + 0.91		
				6	<i>omio + omig</i>	0.94 + 0.93		
				6	<i>yava/magn + ates</i> <i>yava + magn</i>	0.58 + 0.99 0.97 + 0.68		
			(2, 20)	1	<i>yava/magn/ates/atel + omio/omig</i>	0.53 [0.51–0.55] + 0.91 [0.90–0.92]		
		mxpl	4	Merge	(0.1, 10)	4	<i>berl + neov</i> <i>spec + chic</i>	0.51 [0.48–0.54] + 0.80 [0.78–0.83] 0.64 [0.60–0.68] + 0.73 [0.69–0.76]
					(0.1, 20) ³	4	<i>berl + neov</i> <i>spec + chic</i>	0.52 + 0.81 0.62 + 0.71
(2, 20)	4				<i>berl + neov</i> <i>spec + chic</i>	0.44 [0.40–0.48] + 0.79 [0.77–0.80] 0.62 [0.59–0.74] + 0.70 [0.67–0.81]		
Split	(0.1, 10)				2	<i>berl/neov + spec/chic</i>	0.75 [0.73–0.77] + 0.89 [0.87–0.90]	
					2	<i>berl + neov</i>	0.28 [0.24–0.32] + 0.75 [0.72–0.78]	

				<i>spec + chic</i>	<i>0.67 [0.64–0.70] + 0.76 [0.72–0.78]</i>	
			(0.1, 20) ³	3	berl/neov + spec/chic	0.74 + 0.89
					<i>berl + neov</i>	<i>0.48 + 0.77</i>
					spec + chic	0.63 + 0.73
					<i>berl + neov</i>	<i>0.48 + 0.77</i>
			(2, 20)	2	berl/neov + spec/chic	0.75 [0.73–0.77] + 0.89 [0.87–0.90]
					<i>berl + neov</i>	<i>0.50 [0.47–0.54] + 0.80 [0.78–0.82]</i>
					<i>spec + chic</i>	<i>0.63 [0.59–0.67] + 0.73 [0.69–0.76]</i>

¹Slashes indicate that populations were considered a single group in HHSD; plus signs indicate comparison of groups considered by HHSD.

²Row text is bolded if split or merge was accepted; text that is not bolded and italicized indicates the split or merge was not accepted.

³We conducted runs with migration priors of (0.1, 20) with a previous version of HHSD that did not include HPD estimates.

Abbreviations: *gdi*: genealogical divergence index; HPD: highest posterior density; arce: Arcelia form; atel: Atenquique long form; ates: Atenquique short form; berl: *R. berlandieri*; chic: *R. spectabilis*, southern group; flor: *R. f. floresi*; forr: *R. f. forreri*; hilli: *R. f. hillisi*; magn: *R. magnaocularis*; miad: *R. f. miadis*; neov: *R. b. neovolcanica*; omio: *R. omiltemana* from Oaxaca; omig: *R. omiltemana* from Guerrero; spec: *R. spectabilis*, northern group; yava: *R. yavapaiensis*.

Table S4. Taxonomic changes over time in the accepted number of species within the *Rana pipiens* complex (at the time) and the cumulative number of species that are currently recognized. Results are plotted in *SI Appendix, Figure S2*.

Year	No. species newly described	No. species subsumed/sunk	Change in species number	Net number of species	Newly described species	Cumulative species currently recognized
1782	1		1	1	<i>pipiens</i>	1
1802			0	1	<i>halecina</i>	1
1825	1		1	2	<i>palustris</i>	2
1826	1		1	3	<i>utricularia,</i> <i>pardalis</i>	2
1852	1		1	4	<i>areolata</i>	3
1854	1		1	5	<i>montezumae</i>	4
1855	1		1	6	<i>capito</i>	5
1856			0	6	<i>oxyrhynchus</i>	5
1859	1		1	7	<i>berlandieri</i>	6
1865			0	7	<i>adrita</i>	6
1875	1	2	-1	6	<i>onca</i>	7
1877	1		1	7	<i>macroglossa</i>	8
1878			0	7	<i>circulosa</i>	8
1883	1		1	8	<i>forreri</i>	9
1886		1	-1	7	<i>draytoni</i>	9
1889			0	7	<i>virescens</i>	9
1893	1		1	8	<i>octoplicata,</i> <i>fisheri</i>	10
1899	1		1	9	<i>trilobata</i>	10
1900	1		1	10	<i>omiltemana</i>	11
1906		1	-1	9		11
1912	1		1	10	<i>austriicola</i>	11
1915	1		1	11	<i>sphenocephala</i>	12
1917	1		1	12	<i>aesopus</i>	12
1919		2	-2	10		12
1922	3	1	2	12	<i>burnsi,</i> <i>kandiyohi, noblei</i>	12
1927	1	3	-2	10		12
1929	1		1	11	<i>miadis</i>	13
1937			0	11	<i>brachycephala</i>	13
1940	1		1	12	<i>sevosa</i>	14
1942		1	-1	11	<i>megapoda</i>	15
1943		1	-1	10		15
1947		1	-1	9		15
1949		1	-1	8		15

1951		1	-1	7		15
1957	2	1	1	8	<i>dunni</i>	16
1959	1		1	9	<i>taylori</i>	17
1965		1	-1	8		17
1973	2		2	10	<i>blairi</i>	18
1974	2		2	12	<i>magnaocularis</i>	19
1978	1		1	13		19
1979	1		1	14	<i>chiricahuensis</i>	20
1981	2		2	16	<i>brownorum</i>	21
1982	1		1	17		21
1984	1		1	18	<i>yavapaiensis</i>	22
					<i>neovolcanica,</i>	
					<i>spectabilis,</i>	
1985	4		4	22	<i>tlaloci</i>	25
1987	2		2	24		25
1993			0	24	<i>subaquavocalis</i>	25
1996	1		1	25	<i>chichicuahutla</i>	26
2001	1		1	26		26
2003	1		1	27	<i>lemosespinali</i>	27
2004			0	27	<i>burnsorum</i>	27
2014	1		1	28	<i>kauffeldi</i>	28
2018	1		1	29	<i>lenca</i>	29
2022	2		2	31	<i>cora, floresi</i>	31
2023	2		2	33	<i>hillisi, adleri</i>	33
2024		10	-10	23		23

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